

PTSD Treatment Literature

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Abstract

PTSD cases represents a growing expense for society and the U.S. Veterans Administration since the proportion of veterans with PTSD symptom exceed proportions in the civilian population. The PTSD literature is not in agreement whether a “cure” for PTSD exists and what a “cure” would look like. A wide variety of PTSD treatment approaches have been applied with differing results regarding mitigation of symptoms and the duration of the mitigation. Authoritative sources from the United States, the United Kingdom and Australia identify specific psychotherapies as the “gold standard” for treatment. Despite warnings, patients have been prescribed pharmacological remedies. In the United States only two drugs have been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for PTSD treatment. However, a wider array of drugs has been prescribed. The US Department of Veteran Affairs (DVA) specifically concluded that benzodiazepines use is not a recommended strategy for PTSD treatment, yet it is dispensed to veterans, although at a more limited rate than previously. Knowledge about relative effectiveness of alternative treatments is still emerging. As indicated by changes in US guidelines, the conventional wisdom regarding PTSD treatment is fluid and in need of periodic reassessment. Research on new types of treatment should be ongoing.

Introduction

PTSD remains an expensive and vexing problem for veterans and others. The calculated economic costs are considerable. One study estimated that in 2018 the economic burden of PTSD in the U.S. exceeded \$232.2 billion or \$19,630 per individual with PTSD. Costs included those linked to research, treatments, unemployment, productivity loss, and premature mortality [1]. A PTSD diagnosis has been found to increase the likelihood of being homeless by 150% [2]. PTSD has also been linked to suicide in both the general and military veteran population. According to the US Centers of Disease Control and Prevention, 8.3 million adults aged 18 or older experienced suicidal thoughts in 2008 for a prevalence rate of 3.7%. Various studies have found evidence of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) acting as a strong risk factor for suicidal behaviors. For example, a national Canadian study, found that suicide attempts were 2.4 times more likely among people with PTSD, after adjusting for demographic and psychiatric variables [3]. A national study of Denmark’s population indicated that citizens diagnosed with PTSD had 5.3 times greater odds of

suicide than citizens without the diagnosis, adjusted for other variables [4]. A wide body of research indicates that suicides and PTSD are significantly higher among US veterans than US civilians [5]. Given the high cost of PTSD it is incumbent upon those in the health profession to critically explore the efficacy of specific treatment and the potential for innovation. Gaining a firmer understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of various treatments for PTSD will benefit clients, academic and practitioners.

Methods

A google search was conduct using the terms PTSD treatments scholarly articles and PTSD research scholarly article. Information was obtained in late February of 2024 revealing more than 3.4 million search results for PTSD research and 2.4 million search results for PTSD treatment. Large well-funded organizations such as the American Psychiatric Association (APA), the Department of Defense, Department of Veterans Administration (DoD/DVA), the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and the Australian Government National Health and Medical Resource Council are discussed below. These represent

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recommendations from authoritative bodies from the nations of the US, UK, and Australia.

Results

Numerous organizations such as US American Psychological Association (APA), the Veterans Health Administration and Department of Defense (VA/DoD) present detailed guidelines for treatment of PTSD [6]. Recommendations from the USA's APA, VA/DoD, the UK's National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), and the Australian Government National Health and Medical Resource Council are presented below.

APA Recommendations for PTSD Treatment (USA)

The APA considered four factors in their recommendations for PTSD treatment: (1) overall strength of the evidence for the treatment; (2) the balance of benefits and harms; (3) patient values and preferences for treatment; and (4) the applicability of evidence to various populations. Recommendations were offered on the efficacy of both psychological and pharmacological interventions. The recommendations were not intended to be mandates or to supplant clinician judgment, but to help guide health care providers and their patients in making decisions about treatment options. The publication of the PTSD guideline marked the first time that APA has published clinical practice guidelines in psychology rather than psychiatry. The guideline "strongly recommended" the treatments of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) Cognitive Processing Therapy (CPT), Cognitive Therapy (CT), and Prolonged Exposure (PE).

In addition, the APA Guideline conditionally recommended three psychotherapies and four medications. A conditional recommendation indicated that treatments could lead to good outcomes; however, the evidence may not be as strong, or the balance of treatment benefits and possible harms may be less favorable, or the intervention may be less applicable across treatment settings or subgroups of individuals with PTSD. The APA conditionally recommended the use of (1) Brief Eclectic Psychotherapy (BEP), (2) eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR), and (3) narrative exposure therapy (NET). The APA found insufficient evidence to recommend "for or against" the treatments of Seeking Safety (SS) or relaxation (RLX). The following four medications were suggested: fluoxetine, paroxetine, sertraline, and venlafaxine. Insufficient evidence was found to recommend "for or against" offering the medications risperidone and topiramate. APA Guidelines included reviews of clinical trials conducted prior to and following 2012. To determine whether recommendations based on that evidence would hold up in the face of new evidence, a revised search was carried out to identify trials published between May 25, 2012, and June 1, 2016. Based on the new trials, it was determined that

recommendations for all the interventions except EMDR and NET were unlikely to change [7].

The APA guidelines weighed treatment benefits and harms in determining whether benefits "clearly outweigh," "slightly outweigh," or a "benefits and harms/ burdens are balanced." Treatments that were categorized as benefits "clearly outweigh" included the CBT, CPT, CT, PE, EMDR and the medication Paroxetine. Treatments categorized as benefits "slightly outweigh" harms/burdens included Brief Eclectic Psychotherapy (BEP), Fluoxetine, and Sertraline. A balance between benefits and harms/burdens was found for Risperidone and Topiramate [7]. In contrast to the research of other organizations, the APA guideline did not address complementary or alternative treatments, PTSD prevention, PTSD treatment in children, or cost. It was the hope of members of the research panel that future iterations of the guideline would include these topics.

Veterans Administration/Department of Defense (VA/DoD) Recommendations for PTSD Treatment (USA)

In 2023, the VA and DoD updated their Clinical Practice Guideline for the Management of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Acute Stress Disorder [8]. The individual psychotherapy treatments of CPT, EMDR, and PE as well as the medications paroxetine, sertraline and venlafaxine received a "strong for" recommendations. When both psychotherapies and pharmacotherapies were available and feasible, psychotherapies were recommended. The Guideline recognized that time demands could factor into use and feasibility determinations. In support of the recommendation for psychotherapeutic treatment modalities over pharmacotherapy various studies were cited [9–11]. Supporting their preference for psychotherapies, the VA/DoD Guideline noted that pharmacologic treatments are generally associated with a higher risk of side effects and over time, the positive effects of medication treatment decrease or disappear when medications are stopped. The "strong for" recommendation for psychotherapies were perceived to reduce depression, improve functioning, and improve quality of life. The risks associated with the above-mentioned psychotherapy therapies were found to be low.

A broad array of other psychotherapy treatments was considered by the VA/DoD. "Weak for" recommendations were issued for the following treatments: (1) Ehlers' Cognitive Therapy for PTSD, (2) Present-Centered Therapy, and (3) Written Exposure Therapy (WET). Justifications for the recommendations cited relevant literature [12,13]. The VA/DoD found "insufficient evidence to recommend for or against" a wide array of treatments including but not limited to Couples Therapies, Behavioral Family Therapy, Structured Approach Therapy, Cognitive Behavioral

Conjoint Therapy, Trauma-Informed Guilt Reduction, Trauma Management Therapy, Accelerated Resolution Therapy, Adaptive Disclosure, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy, Brief Eclectic Psychotherapy, Dialectical Behavior Therapy, and Emotional Freedom Techniques.

In 2022, a “strong for” recommendation for the treatment of PTSD was issued for only three drugs (paroxetine, sertraline, and venlafaxine) [14]. This finding represents a change from the 2017 VA/DoD PTSD Guideline, which in addition to the three above cited drugs also recommended the drug fluoxetine. Recent studies, however, found no benefit from the use of fluoxetine. Industry-sponsored Randomized Control Trials found sertraline and paroxetine provided a clinically significant benefit. There was no benefit found in clinician-rated PTSD scores in any of the two sertraline trials that were carried out in a veteran population. The VA/DoD acknowledged the existence of a “Black Box” warning by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) on the use of various antidepressants. In their warning, the FDA noted that antidepressants raise the risk of suicidal thinking and behavior (suicidality) among children, adolescents, and young adults. The suicide warning did not apply to adults over the age of 24. Despite the FDA warning, the VA/DoD noted that the benefits of treatment with paroxetine, sertraline, and venlafaxine outweighed the potential harm. Given the lack of evidence and the possibility of adverse effects the VA/DoD recommendation was “neither for nor against” specific psychedelic agents.

“Strong against” determinations were made regarding cannabis, cannabis derivatives and benzodiazepines (Xanax, Klonopin, and Valium). The “strong against” recommendation for benzodiazepines referred to studies that indicated a lack of effectiveness on PTSD symptoms, benzodiazepine misuse, and cognitive changes, especially in the elderly [14,15]. The VA/DoD noted some interest in benzodiazepines because of short-term anxiety relief, however, these medications were found to be ineffective in the long term and potentially harmful. Concerns surrounded substance abuse and effects on elderly patients. There was no evidence of long-term benefit, therefore it was determined that the potential harms of these medications exceeded the benefits.

A “strong against” recommendation was issued for cannabis or cannabis derivatives for the treatment of PTSD due to a lack of well-designed randomized clinical trials evaluating the efficacy of cannabis derivatives and the serious side effects associated with their use [16]. Studies cited by the VA/DoD linked cannabis use to impaired attention, impaired memory, impaired driving ability and impaired IQ. More troubling, some research found a link between early and persistent cannabis use

and the emergence of psychosis [17]. Other adverse psychiatric outcomes associated with marijuana use included suicide attempts, paranoia, and agitation [18]. Based on the available evidence the VA/DoD concluded that potential harm of cannabis as a treatment outweighed potential benefits. An important consideration in the VA/DoD reporting was cost. According to the VA/DoD, the cost of psychotherapy clearly exceeded that of pharmacological approaches because psychotherapy treatments typically required at least ten weekly sessions of therapy. However, various studies indicate that the use of trauma-focused therapies represented the “gold standard” for treatment [19].

The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence PTSD Treatment Recommendations (UK)

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) offered PTSD treatment recommendations for both children and adults. NICE recommended: (1) considering individual trauma-focused CBT interventions for children (aged 5 to 6 years) with a diagnosis of PTSD or clinically important symptoms of PTSD for more than 1 month after a traumatic event; (2) considering an individual trauma-focused CBT intervention for individuals aged 7 to 17 years with a diagnosis of PTSD or clinically important symptoms of PTSD who have symptoms between 1 and 3 months after a traumatic event; and (3) offering an individual trauma-focused CBT intervention to children and young people aged 7 to 17 years with a diagnosis of PTSD or clinically important symptoms of PTSD who had symptoms more than 3 months after a traumatic event. NICE recommended EMDR (for people aged 7 to 17 years who had prolonged symptoms) only if they did not respond to or engage with trauma-focused CBT. The NICE Guideline included but were not limited to providing individual trauma-focused CBT interventions and providing ongoing supervision. Treatments were to be age and development specific. There was a specific recommendation against the offering of pharmacological treatments for children and young people aged under 18 years [20].

PTSD treatments for adults included the psychotherapies CPT, CT, NET, and PE. NICE recommended: (1) EMDR for those who had symptoms between one and three months after a non-combat-related trauma, if the person preferred EMDR; (2) EMDR for those who had symptoms more than three months after a noncombat-related trauma; and (3) trauma-focused computerized CBT for those who had symptom more than three months after a traumatic event, if they preferred the treatment to face-to-face trauma-focused CBT or EMDR. The computer option was only to be considered if patients were not at risk of harm to themselves or others. A recommendation was made to not offer pharmacological treatments,

including benzodiazepines, to prevent PTSD in adults. The recommendation supported considering venlafaxine or a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), such as sertraline, for adults with a diagnosis of PTSD if the person preferred drug treatments. NICE recommended considering the use of antipsychotics (such as risperidone) if patients exhibited severe hyperarousal or psychosis, or symptoms had not responded to other drug or psychological treatments.

Australian Guideline for the Treatment of Adults

The Australian Guideline for the treatment of PTSD provided several recommendations about how to respond to the needs and preferences of traumatized patients [21]. Guideline recommendations were made under the rubric of “strong” (moderate to strong confidence in evidence) or “conditional” (lower certainty in the evidence). Recommendations were also made for interventions that were considered “promising.” These interventions were thought to warrant further research.

Interventions were identified for both adults, and children/adolescents. A “strong” recommendation was made for trauma focused CBT for children and adolescents. Only a “conditional” recommendation was made for EMDR therapy when considering this age group. The Guideline suggested EMDR could be offered to young people when trauma-focused CBT was unavailable or unacceptable. The Guideline for children and adults found insufficient evidence to make a “strong” recommendation for any pharmacological intervention.

Treatment modalities for adults addressed both (1) interventions after three months and (2) interventions within the first three months of trauma. When interventions in the first three months were considered, a “strong” recommendation was made for a stepped/collaborative care model where individuals would receive evidence-based care commensurate with the severity and complexity of their need. “Conditional” recommendations were offered for cognitive behavioral therapies (including prolonged exposure, cognitive processing therapy, and cognitive therapy), and EMDR. “Conditional” interventions were suggested in preference to doing nothing.

When regular interventions or interventions after three months were considered, strong recommendation were made for CPT, CPT, PE, and trauma-focused CBT. Only a “conditional” recommendation was offered for an array of interventions that included NET, stress inoculation training (SIT), and trauma-focused CBT (group). In addition to these psychological intervention recommendations, recommendations were also offered regarding pharmacology. Only a “conditional” recommendation was offered for sertraline, paroxetine, fluoxetine, and venlafaxine. These treatments were suggested when a patient was

unwilling or not in a position to engage in or access recommended psychological therapy, or the patient was not sufficiently stable to commence recommended psychological therapy.

The Australian Guideline identified an array of interventions that were classified as “promising and warranted further research.” These “promising” interventions were not recommended for the treatment of PTSD. For children and adolescence within the first three months of trauma, the Australia Guideline recommendation of “promising” included self-directed online psychoeducation. After three months recommendations included: group trauma-focused cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for children, Narrative Exposure Therapy for children (KidNET), and parent–child relationship enhancement (play therapy), among others. For adults in the first three months, the Australian Guideline recommended brief individual trauma processing therapy, brief dyadic therapies, internet-based CBT, empowerment, structured writing therapy and hydrocortisone. For adults after three months, an array of psychological and non-psychological interventions was discussed. Psychological interventions such as couples TF-CBT, group and individual (combined) TF-CB, virtual reality therapy, written exposure therapy (WET) were identified as “promising and warranting further research.”

In contrast to other PTSD studies, the Australian Guideline introduced several non-psychological and non-pharmacological intervention that were viewed as holding promise. The Guideline states that there was emerging evidence for nontraditional types of interventions that included: (1) acupuncture, (2) mindfulness-based stress reduction, (3) neurofeedback, (4) repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation, (5) transcendental meditation, and (6) yoga. Regarding pharmacological interventions, the Guideline stated that there was emerging evidence for the use of both Ketamine and Quetiapine. However, the Guideline noted that where medication is indicated for the treatment of PTSD, the suggested use is for an SSRI or SNRI antidepressant.

Discussion

The existing literature indicates that psychotherapies such as Cognitive Processing Therapy (CPT), Prolonged Exposure Therapy (PE), Eye Movement, Desensitization, and Restructuring (EMDR) are strongly recommended treatments for PTSD. Patients have expressed a preference for such psychotherapies over pharmacotherapy. A disadvantage of psychotherapies relates to its cost which are higher in the short run. However, in the long run research has found psychotherapy to be more cost effective because of the higher relapse rate associated with medication [23].

Given the incidence of PTSD among veterans of the wars in Iraq and Afghanistan, demands on VA hospitals can overwhelm resources. Under resource constraints, pressures can mount for pharmacological options despite a recognition of a “gold standard” for specific psychotherapies. PTSD treatment costs have escalated over time. Estimates of PTSD incidence during the U.S. wars in Vietnam, Iraq and Afghanistan vary widely. Estimates of combat-related PTSD in U.S. military veterans since the Vietnam War ranged from approximately 2% to 17% [24]. Data from the 2018 Health Related Behavior Survey of military personnel indicated that among active-duty service members, 17.9% experienced at least one of three mental health problems, probable depression (9.4%), probable generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) (14.2%), or probable PTSD (8.5%) [25].

A review of the PTSD literature identifies a few issues that deserve greater attention. Currently, only sertraline and paroxetine are approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for PTSD. However, both the VA/DoD and APA have given approval to a larger number of medications. The VA/DoD has consistently issued strongly negative assessments of benzodiazepines (such as Valium, Xanax, and Klonopin). Despite warnings, until recently, the Veterans Administration has widely dispensed benzodiazepines. According to the U.S. Veterans Administration, 30% of PTSD patients were given prescriptions for benzodiazepines in fiscal year 2012. Perhaps due to ongoing research and pressure to change policy, 9.1% of PTSD patients were prescribed benzodiazepines in Fiscal Year 2020 [26]. However, if VA/DoD guidelines were followed, the VA should prohibit all use.

The benefits of psychotherapies must be weighed against the cost and viability of other treatments. The use of drugs that are not approved by the FDA and the use of proscribed drugs raises red flags. More research as well as more attention to negative side effects of specific drugs is needed. In recent years, a variety of innovative approaches to treating PTSD have been introduced. More research is needed in terms of the costs and benefits of these treatments. Traditional trauma-focused approaches were found to only work for some patients and some research emphasizes the need for novel approaches [27].

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Conclusions

PTSD remains a serious problem. A wide array of treatments has been proposed with specific psychotherapies recognized as the “gold standard.” Despite warnings by government agencies such as the US FDA and US VA/DoD, various patients have been prescribed pharmacological remedies. Two findings from a review of the PTSD literature stand out (1) a

wider array of drugs are administered to patients than are formally approved by official government agencies; and (2) governmental agencies specifically concluded that benzodiazepines use is not a recommended strategy for PTSD treatment, yet it is dispensed to US veterans, although at a more limited rate than previously.

More research is needed to discover effective and cost-efficient treatments for PTSD. Psychotherapies remain the gold standard for treatment. Knowledge about relative effectiveness of alternative treatments is still emerging. As indicated by changes in the US VA/DoD guidelines, the conventional wisdom regarding PTSD treatment is fluid and in need of periodic reassessment. Research on new types of treatment should be ongoing.

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